

SEPARATION OF IRON, ALUMINIUM AND TITANIUM

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A convenient and easily workable process has been worked out for the separation of iron, aluminium and titanium from each other. The basis of separation depends on the use of H_2O_2 which forms with titanium soluble salts of pertitanic acid, the latter forming pertitanates on reacting with alkali carbonates or hydroxides. Pertitanates on boiling forms a quantitative precipitate which can be dissolved in HCl and reprecipitated as titanium hydroxide.

Separation of iron, aluminium and titanium from each other has been the subject of much discussions and various methods have been published on this subject from time to time, but none is so satisfactory.

Hydrogen peroxide produces a characteristic yellow to orange coloration with acid titanium solution, while with the other two elements, viz, iron and aluminium, it does not do so.

A characteristic property of the solution of titanium salts is the ease with which they undergo hydrolysis on boiling with the precipitation of metatitanic acid. Titanium is separated from iron by hydrolysis with sodium or ammonium thiosulphate in acid solution along with aluminium, if present. The two elements are then separated by fusing the ignited precipitate with sodium carbonate, and extracting with water. Sodium aluminate will pass into solution, whereas sodium titanate being insoluble will remain behind.

The above standard process is very troublesome, lengthy and not free from complication. During the hydrolysis of titanium and aluminium salts by means of ammonium thiosulphate, the acidity is to be carefully regulated.

In another method buffer solutions are used to adjust acidity.

The most satisfactory method of separation of titanium from aluminium is by means of cupferron. This reagent precipitates titanium from an acidified solution leaving aluminium in solution. But it does not afford a means to separate this element from iron.

The process described by Gooch (*Chem. News*, 1885, 52, 55, 68), though recommended for the separation of the elements, is not very convenient to work up. It is lengthy and troublesome. It involves too many fusions. Moreover, iron is to be separated by means of tartaric acid and sulphuretted hydrogen and the tartaric acid is to be destroyed for further operations by lengthy processes which have made it not very smooth and easily workable. Investigations have been made in this direction and a convenient and easily workable process for the separation of iron, aluminium and titanium from each other, has been worked out.

The basis of this process is that pertitanic acid, formed by the action of hydrogen peroxide on a soluble salt of titanium, reacts with alkali carbonates

or hydroxides to form pertitanates. These pertitanates are soluble in the cold but separate out as insoluble curdy white precipitate either on boiling or on standing even in the cold. Quantitative precipitation takes place when the solution is boiled. This precipitate is not a true pertitanate but another form of pertitanic acid, as it is not soluble either in cold or in hot water. On the other hand, this precipitate readily dissolves in hydrochloric acid producing the characteristic orange colour of pertitanic acid. So if to the acidified solution of iron, aluminium and titanium salts, hydrogen peroxide is added, orange-yellow colour of pertitanic acid is developed. On being carefully neutralised with sodium carbonate solution the colour will be discharged and soluble sodium salts of pertitanic acid will form. To keep aluminium also in solution alkali carbonate containing 2 to 3 g. of caustic soda is added in excess (alkali carbonate in presence of hydrogen peroxide can itself keep aluminium in solution). Only iron will be precipitated as brown hydroxide which can be filtered and washed with the alkali carbonate solution. The filtrate is made to boil when the soluble salt of titanium either breaks down or is hydrolysed and a curdy white precipitate separates out. This is washed with sodium carbonate solution and is kept ready for the estimation of titanium. The filtrate contains all the aluminium. It is acidified with hydrochloric acid and aluminium is precipitated with ammonia.

The following precautions have been found necessary.

1. Too much hydrogen peroxide should be avoided.
2. Alkali carbonates are preferable to hydroxides.
3. As the precipitate separates out as a white curdy mass on standing (perhaps due to hydrolysis), the solution should be filtered first immediately after neutralisation with sodium carbonate.
4. The operation should be conducted in the cold and preferably in the sulphuric acid medium.

EXPERIMENTAL

Procedure.—The slightly acid solution of iron, aluminium and titanium containing the elements to the extent of 0.05 to 0.1g. was taken in a 400 c.c. beaker. About 5 c.c. of hydrogen peroxide was added to it to fully develop the colour of pertitanic acid. To this cold solution, 10% sodium carbonate solution was carefully added till neutralised and iron was just precipitated. At this stage more sodium carbonate solution (25 to 30 c.c.) containing about 2-3g. of caustic soda was added and the solution well stirred for a minute or so with a glass rod to bring aluminium and titanium into solution. It was filtered through a Whatman filter paper No. 41. In order to ensure quick filtering, the filter paper should be washed intermittently with a jet of slightly warm water (not hot water). The precipitate was thoroughly washed with 10% sodium carbonate solution. The filtrate and washings were collected together.

The iron precipitate was washed again with hot water and dissolved in sulphuric acid. If any titanium were suspected in the iron solution, it could be reprecipitated with 10% sodium carbonate solution as above and the filtrate and washings to be added to the main filtrate. By this time iron will be completely free from titanium. The iron precipitate was washed again with sodium carbonate solution and then with hot water and dissolved in hydrochloric acid. Iron can be finished either gravimetrically or volumetrically.

The combined filtrate contains all the aluminium and titanium. It was heated on the hot plate and the solution was boiled down if the volume were large enough. White curdy precipitate of a titanium salt fell down. Care should be taken to see that all the hydrogen peroxide is decomposed, otherwise it tends to retain some titanium in solution. The solution was cooled and filtered. The white precipitate was washed four times with hot 10% solution of sodium carbonate. Washings with distilled water will hydrolyse the salt and colloidal titanic acid will pass through the filter paper into the filtrate.

The precipitate was dissolved in hydrochloric acid. Orange-yellow pertitanic acid colour developed. The filter paper was washed with water to remove the stain of yellow colour. The solution was boiled on the hot plate till the yellow colour disappeared and the liquid became colorless. Titanium was precipitated from the solution either with ammonia or with ammonium thiosulphate and was finished by igniting the precipitate to TiO_2 . The filtrate from the precipitate contained aluminium. It was carefully acidified with hydrochloric acid and then made ammoniacal with ammonia. Aluminium hydroxide was precipitated. It was filtered, thoroughly washed with hot water to free it from alkali and ignited to Al_2O_3 .

Good results are obtained if the experiment is done carefully.

In conducting the experiments solutions of iron, aluminium and titanium salts were prepared and mixed in varying proportions.

Preparation of Iron Solution.—Pure ferrous ammonium sulphate (39.5 g.) was dissolved in water, acidified with enough sulphuric acid to prevent hydrolysis. The solution was transferred to a 1000 c.c. measuring flask and diluted to the mark. The solution was then standardised against 0.1N potassium permanganate solution and the iron content per c.c. of this solution was found to be 0.0055 g. per c.c.

Preparation of Aluminium Solution.—Pure aluminium wire (1 g. of 99.94% purity) was accurately weighed and dissolved in 30 c.c. of dilute hydrochloric acid (1:4). When the aluminium was completely dissolved, the solution was made to boil for a few minutes, then allowed to cool and the volume was then made up to 500 c.c. in a measuring flask; 1 c.c. of this solution contained 0.002 g. of aluminium.

Preparation of Titanium Solution.—Pure titanium dioxide (1 g.) was weighed out in a pyrex beaker and dissolved in 50 c.c. of concentrated sulphuric acid and 20 g. of fused potassium bisulphate added and heated when a perfectly

clear liquid was obtained. Heating was continued for sometime after which the content was cooled. The mass was then taken up with dilute sulphuric acid and the volume diluted to 250 c.c., 1 c.c. of this solution contained 0.0024 g. of titanium.

TABLE I

	Sample taken.	Found.	Calculated.
1.	10 c.c. of $\text{FeAmSO}_4 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.055 g. Fe)	Fe, 0.053 g.	0.055 g.
	20 c.c. TiO_2 soln. (0.048 g. Ti)	Ti, 0.045	0.048
	20 c.c. aluminium soln. (0.040 g. Al)	Al, 0.038	0.040
2.	20 c.c. FeAmSO_4 (0.110 g. Fe)	Fe, 0.1070	0.110
	30 c.c. TiO_2 soln. (0.072 g. Ti)	Ti, 0.069	0.072
	30 c.c. Al soln. (0.060 g. Al)	Al, 0.058	0.060
3.	15 c.c. FeAmSO_4 (0.0825 g. Fe)	Fe, 0.080	0.0825
	40 c.c. TiO_2 soln. (0.0960 g. Ti)	Ti, 0.091	0.0960
	40 c.c. Al soln. (0.080 g. Al)	Al, 0.0780	0.080

*Application of the above Process in the Estimation of Titanium
in Ferro-titanium*

Ferro-titanium is an alloy of titanium and iron. Titanium content of this alloy generally varies up to 30%. The alloy was crushed and ground in an agate mortar to a fineness of 100 mesh. This powdered material (0.5 g.) was weighed out in a 500 c.c. tall beaker and decomposed with 1:4 sulphuric acid and the mass taken to fumes. It was cooled and the content dissolved in dilute sulphuric acid. The solution was then filtered and the residue, which was mainly silica contaminated with a little titania, was washed and finally ignited in a platinum crucible and weighed. The ignited mass was then treated with hydrofluoric acid with a drop or two of sulphuric acid. It was carefully ignited and weighed. The loss in weight was silica. The residue, if any, was fused with potassium bisulphate and the mass was extracted with dilute sulphuric acid. The solution was added to the main filtrate. The filtrate was carefully neutralised with ammonia till a brownish precipitate just appeared. The precipitate was dissolved with dilute sulphuric acid and the solution was made distinctly acidic. About 5 c.c. of hydrogen peroxide (20 vol.) was added to fully develop the colour of pertitanic acid. At this stage the solution was neutralised with 10% solution of sodium carbonate until iron was completely precipitated. The reagent was added in excess together with 2-3 g. of NaOH. During this process the solution was stirred vigorously. It was continued two to three minutes more after the precipitation was complete. The whole of iron was precipitated and titanium went into solution. The solution was then quickly filtered. To ensure

quick filtration a platinum cone may be used, and a gentle suction applied. The precipitate was washed with a warm (50°) solution of sodium carbonate. The washings were added to the main filtrate. The clear filtrate was then made to boil. A curdy precipitate fell down. When the volume of the solution was diminished to half its original volume and all the hydrogen peroxide decomposed, the beaker was removed from the hot plate and the precipitate allowed to settle. It was filtered through a Whatman filter paper No. 41. It was washed with dilute sodium carbonate solution and dissolved in hydrochloric acid. The filter paper was washed with distilled water till the yellow stain disappeared. The acidity of the solution was then adjusted and titanium was precipitated from the boiling solution by means of sodium thiosulphate. The precipitate was then filtered, washed and ignited as TiO_2 .

In this experiment a sample of ferro-titanium containing about 29% of titanium, determined by the ordinary thiosulphate process, was employed.

TABLE II

Sample taken.	Titanium found by	
	above process.	ordinary process.
0.520 g.	28.56%	28.75%
0.452	28.60	28.75
0.305	28.58	28.75

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